

FEATURES OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF DISSEMINATED ECHINOCOCCOSIS OF THE ABDOMINAL CAVITY

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The relevance of the problem. In the surgical treatment of echinococcosis, especially disseminated echinococcosis (DE) of the abdominal cavity, the main unresolved issues are reduced to determining the volume of preoperative preparation, questions of the stages of surgical interventions, determining tactics in relation to access and choosing the most appropriate method of eliminating the residual cavity and the method of treatment of the residual cavity (RC).

Objective of the study: optimization of surgical tactics in patients with disseminated echinococcosis of the abdominal cavity.

Material and methods. The work is based on the analysis of the results of treatment of 87 patients with disseminated echinococcosis of the abdominal cavity who received inpatient treatment at the AndGosMI clinic in the period from 2017 to 2022. All patients were divided into 2 groups: comparison – 51 (58.6%) patients who received treatment in 2017-2017 by traditional methods; main - 36 (41.3%) patients who received inpatient treatment in 2018-2022. our improved methods of treatment.

At the same time, in the comparison group, primary disseminated echinococcosis was diagnosed in 22 (43.1%) patients, secondary disseminated - in 13 (25.4%), tertiary disseminated - in 16 (31.3%) patients. In the main group, primary disseminated echinococcosis was diagnosed in 20 (55.5%) patients, secondary disseminated - in 7 (19.4%), tertiary disseminated - in 9 (23.1%) patients.

In the diagnosis, general clinical research methods were used (complaints, anamnesis, objective examination), combined X-ray, ultrasound, and in doubtful cases MSCT. All patients were subjected to surgical treatment.

One of the important stages of the operation is the choice of echinococectomy and elimination of the residual cavity after removal of the parasite elements, depending on the diameter of the EC.

In the comparison group, closed echinococectomy was performed in 8 (19.5%) patients. Of these, in 4 (9.8%) patients, the diameter of cysts reached 5 cm, in 3 (7.3%) - 6-10 cm and in 1 (2.4%) - 11-20 cm.

Semi-closed EE was performed in 12 (29.3%) patients. Of these, the diameter of cysts in 3 (7.3%) patients reached 5 cm, in 4 (9.8%) - 6-10 cm, in 2 (4.9%) - 11-20 cm and in 3 (6.9%) - 21 cm or more. Open EE was performed in 10 (24.4%) patients. Of these, in 2 (4.9%) patients, the cyst diameter was 5 cm, in 2 (4.9%) - 6-10 cm, in 4 (9.8%) - 11-20 cm and in 2 (3.4%) - 21 cm or more. Combined EE was performed in 11 (27.6%) patients. Of these, 4 (9.8%) had a cyst diameter of 5 cm, 5 (12.2%) - 6-10 cm and 2 (4.9%) patients - 11-20 cm

It should be noted that in the comparison group, the isolation of the surgical wound and the surgical space was carried out in a standard way (with large napkins), an alcohol solution of iodine was used to treat the residual cavity, in some cases furacillin, which is confirmed by relapses of echinococcosis in the postoperative period in 5 (12.2%) patients.

In this group of operated patients, the frequency of postoperative complications was higher. This is due to both the nature of the operation and the initially severe general status of patients.

The lack of clear indications when choosing surgical access, the amount of surgical aid, the method of treatment and elimination of OP caused the development of various kinds of postoperative complications and unsatisfactory results in the separated period.

In accordance with the goals and objectives of the study, patients with abdominal DE in the main group - 46 (52.9%), were subject to surgical treatment adhering to optimized surgical tactics from 2018 to 2022.

The identified omissions and errors in the comparison group made it necessary to revise surgical tactics both in terms of preoperative preparation and postoperative management, and in choosing the optimal access, the volume of the operation, as well as in the treatment and elimination of OP during surgery. In patients of the main group during preoperative preparation, we apply a set of measures that should be strictly individual and aimed at eliminating functional disorders from internal organs and systems existing before surgery, as well as preventing all kinds of complications.

Taking the drug "Albendazole" according to the scheme developed in the clinic was carried out in 2 doses at a standard dosage of 10-12 mg / kg of weight per day with mandatory joint intake of vegetable oil. Chemotherapy was also combined with the use of furazolidone 50 mg x 3 times a day, metronidazole 250

mg x 2 times a day. Preventive chemotherapy is aimed at preventing relapse and dissemination of the disease in the postoperative period. For the purpose of immunostimulation– immunomodulin was used - 1.0 mg intramuscularly or immunal 1 tablet 4 times a day. To prevent adhesions in the abdominal cavity, the drug longidase 3000 ME was applied intramuscularly.

In the main group, closed echinococectomy was performed in 12 (26.1%) patients. Of these, in 6 (13.0%) patients, the diameter of cysts reached 5 cm and in (13.0%) - 6-10 cm. Semi-closed EE was performed in 12 (26.1%) patients. Of these, the diameter of cysts in 2 (4.3%) patients reached 5 cm, in 5 (10.9%) - 6-10 cm, in 3 (6.5%) - 11-20 cm and in 2 (4.3%) - 21 cm or more. Open EE was performed in 8 (17.4%) patients. Of these, in 1 (2.2%) patients, the cyst diameter was 5 cm, in 3 (6.5%) - 6-10 cm, in 2 (4.3%) - 11-20 cm and in 2 (4.3%) -21 cm or more. Combined EE was performed in 14 (30.4%) patients. Of these, 3 (6.5%) had a cyst diameter of 5 cm, 3 (6.5%) - 6-10 cm and 5 (10.9%) patients - 11-20 cm and 3 (6.5%) – 21 cm or more. The surface treatment of the fibrous capsule was carried out according to the method developed by us: 10% sodium chloride solution with an exposure of 2 min, furacilin heated to a temperature of 700 C 2 min, 700 alcohol 2 min, and 5% iodine tincture with an exposure of 2 minutes and at the end, electrocoagulation of the inner surface and edges of the fibrous capsule 2 min., only 10 minutes.

Results and discussion. As a result, the number of patients with general postoperative complications in the comparison group was 4 (9.7%), while in the main group – 1 (2.2%) – an improvement of 7.5%, i.e. from 9.7 to 2.2%. The number of patients with complications prevailed in the comparison group – 14 (34.1%), while in the main group – only 3 (6.5%) patients - ($p < 0.001$).

Including in the main group, cases of relaparotomy were also avoided – from 4.9% and mortality - from 2.4% to 0%. Relapse of the disease was noted in 11 (26.8%) patients of the comparison group and in 1 (2.2%) – in the main group.

Conclusion. Complex antiparasitic treatment of the fibrous capsule cavity, chemotherapy of disseminated echinococcosis of the liver in the pre and postoperative period is one of the important aspects, and sometimes the only method contributing to the prevention of recurrent relapses and dissemination.

In the surgical treatment of patients with echinococcosis of the liver, we consider the performance of organ-preserving operations to be a priority. In uncomplicated echinococcosis of the liver, we consider the performance of a closed echinococectomy to be indicated. With supplicated echinococcosis of the

liver, a semi-closed echinococcectomy was performed. Indications for pericystectomy were cases of marginal location of echinococcal cysts, their calcination.

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